

1 **Hippo pathway factor mobilization occurs during lineage commitment in embryonic stem cells.**

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7 We measured total transcription in the inner cell mass (ICM) and the trophectoderm (TE) of the human
8 embryo to understand the mechanisms underlying TE commitment. We describe here mobilization of the
9 Hippo pathway during exit from pluripotency in the TE. Most evident in embryonic stem cells was TEAD3
10 modulation.

11 Citations

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1. Zhao, B., Ye, X., Yu, J., Li, L., Li, W., Li, S., Yu, J., Lin, J.D., Wang, C.Y., Chinnaiyan, A.M. and Lai, Z.C., 2008. TEAD mediates YAP-dependent gene induction and growth control. *Genes & development*, 22(14), pp.1962-1971.